

PREFORMS FOR COMPOSITE PARTS MADE BY TAILORED FIBRE PLACEMENT

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SUMMARY: A special characteristic of fibre reinforced composites is their anisotropic properties. The maximum of the mechanical properties exist only along the fibre direction. The Institute of Polymer Research developed a new textile process for the production of reinforcing structures. This process allows the consequent transfer of calculated results into textile reinforcements, so that the reinforcement has locally varying fibre orientations and quantities. This paper reports on the technology of tailored fibre placement, the advantages and the possibilities of this technology by means of demonstrator parts.

KEYWORDS: composite material, fibre preforming, tailored fibre placement, application

INTRODUCTION

Different structures for reinforced composite parts today are well known. These are produced for instance by weaving, knitting or braiding [1-4]. For the reinforcement of highly loaded composite components the fibres should be arranged in the following way:

- stretched (without waves and twists)
- aligned to the stress field
- constant stress (the cross-section of the component corresponding to the local load)

Common textile structures can sometimes attend this requests in an economical way.

That is why in the Institute of Polymer Research developed a new textile process for the production of reinforcing structures [5,6]. This process allows the consequent transfer of calculated results into textile reinforcements, so that the reinforcement has locally varying fibre orientations and quantities.

ANISOTROPIC MATERIAL BEHAVIOUR

A special characteristic of fibre reinforced composites is their anisotropic properties. This means the properties, especially the mechanical properties like strength or stiffness are dependent on direction. The maximum of these properties exist only along the fibre direction. If the fibre direction differs from that of the applied stress the mechanical properties are reduced. If the angle between the fibre and the load direction differs only 10 degrees then the strength is reduced to 20% of the maximum (see Fig.1) [7].

Fig.1: Relative strength of carbon fibre UD reinforced composite with epoxy resin dependence on the angle between the load and the fibre direction

That is why is the agreement of fibre and the load direction is very important for the properties of a component. Through the maximum exploitation of the fibres very light weight structures are possible. Requirements for this are:

- exact knowledge of the load cases
- small number of load cases
- is it possible to produce textile structures with the necessary fibre orientations?
- can the textile structures be processed to composite components?

TAILORED FIBRE PLACEMENT (TFP)

With tailored fibre placement it is possible to produce reinforcing structures with stress field aligned fibre orientations. This process is based on the well known embroidery technology, which is currently used for decorating fabrics. The principle of the production process is shown in Fig. 2.

Fig. 2: Principle of tailored fibre placement

A roving is fixed through stitches on a base material. Between the stitches the base material can be moved by numeric control in the X,Y direction. The roving is placed on the base material by zig-zag stitches either side of the roving. The roving can be made of carbon, glass fibres or other types of fibres. The base material can be a fabric or a nonwoven. Suitable is a thin glass fibre fabric. In most cases the needle yarn is made of polyester.

Fig. 3 shows the working unit of the fibre placement machine.

Fig.3: Tailored fibre placement machine

The main advantage, compared to the common textile technologies, is the ability to arrange reinforcing fibres in every direction of the reinforcing area from an angle of 0° to 360° . Accumulation of fibres can be achieved by stitching several times across the same area.

MECHANICAL PROPERTIES

Table 1 shows mechanical properties of UD and $0^\circ/90^\circ$ reinforced composites made by TFP. It can be seen that this composite reaches the usual values.

APPLICATIONS

Brake Booster

The brake booster is a component that is used to support the bicycle brake. This component is fixed in front of the brake and prevents deformations of the brake shoe holder devices. The principle function is shown in Fig. 4.

Table 1: Mechanical properties of UD and 0°/90° reinforced composites made by TFP

Bending Test					
fibre	matrix	structure	fibre volume fraction (%)	σ_{\max} (MPa) (coefficient of variation)	E (GPa) (coefficient of variation)
carbon fibre (Tenax HTA)	epoxy	UD	53	1440 (2,2 %)	103,2 (5,9 %)
carbon fibre (Tenax HMS 40)	epoxy	UD	53	1059 (5,0 %)	154,1 (3,3 %)
carbon fibre (Tenax HTA)	epoxy	0°/90°	52	912 (3,2 %)	71,8 (0,7 %)
glass fibre (commingling yarn)	PA6	UD	50	781 (3,6 %)	28,4 (2,0 %)
Tension Test					
carbon fibre (Tenax HTA)	epoxy	UD	48	1438 (3,0 %)	115,0 (1,9 %)
glass fibre (EC 17-1200-G52)	epoxy	UD	53	904 (3,8 %)	42,0 (0,5 %)

Fig. 4: Principle function and load case of the brake booster

Because the brake booster is used as a curved cantilever beam the stress field of this component for the represented load case is easy to determine. The outer areas will be loaded in compression, the inner areas in tension and the middle in shear stress. Therefore the fibres in the outer and in the inner areas should be a in 0° direction and the middle in an angle of $+45^\circ/-45^\circ$. Fig. 5 shows 3 different types of brake boosters.

A brake booster, made of aluminium, is tested as reference for the composite components. The first component type is produced through the use of a special fibre bundle. This fibre bundle, existed of 4 carbon rovings (4 x 12K), held together by axial threads around it. The cross section of this fibre bundle is circular and is fixed on the base material by stitches through the reinforcing fibres.

The second brake booster type is produced though the fixing of a carbon roving (12K) directly on the base material by zig-zag stitches either side of the reinforcing fibres. The used quantity of carbon fibres is the same as for the component type II.

	Aluminium	Type I	Type II
Stiffness in [(N/mm)/g]	1,77	4,06	6,49

Fig. 5. Brake boosters (real size 130 mm x 135 mm) and their properties

RESULTS

Fig. 5 shows furthermore the stiffness depending on the component weight of the brake boosters at the beginning of the loading. The second brake booster shows the best results. The

values for the first component are not so very good, due to follow causing. On the cross points in the middle area (loaded in shear stress) this bundle creating a deviation of the fibre-axis in the third dimension.

The advantage of using a fibre bundle is a higher production rate compared to the second brake booster. But both the first and the second component shows better properties than the aluminium brake booster and it can be seen that the tailored fibre placement gives the possibility of very light weight constructions.

Link Plate

This component is used for full suspension bikes and transmits impulses from the back wheel over struts to the spring unit. The principle function and the load case are shown on Fig. 6

Fig. 6 Principle function and load case of the link plate

The main load is the compression load in the represented area but the requirement is a compression and a tension part from hole to hole. Fig. 7 shows the optimized preform and the component.

Fig.7: Preform and component (real size 115 mm x 60 mm)

The necessary fibres for the compression and tension load are in the outer area and in the middle in UD structure. This UD-structure move to a direction of 30° to the main loaded compression part and prevent the bend of this part. The weight of this link plate is only 27g and the maximum transmitted force is higher than 10 kN (determined in an experiment). The result of this force is a compression stress over 1000 MPa in the main loaded area. In the testing phase it was not possible to introduce higher loads, because the load was introduced through a bolt with a diameter of only 6 mm and this bolt failed at higher loads.

Bicycle Frame

One of the most interesting components for bicycles is the frame. The requirements, such as maximum loads, drive comfort and minimum production costs on a carbon frame are very high. The frame of a bicycle will be mainly loaded in torsion in one direction and in bending in two directions.

Fig. 8: Main load directions in a bicycle frame

The next figure shows the developed frame.

Fig. 9: Carbon bicycle frame

One of the main problems of this frame is the ordered design of this frame. In the area from the seat to the pedal crankcase, this frame has a very complex shape, so that it is not possible to place the reinforcing fibres optimal on this contour. That is why we developed a reinforcing structure with 4 walls in this area (see Fig 10).

Fig. 10: Reinforcing structure of the frame

In this way it is possible to place the carbon fibres in this area in a straight line. Most fibres in this area are placed in 0° direction (direction from seat to pedal crankcase). Fig. 10 shows the directions of the fibres in the other areas. In the part from the steering unit to the pedal crankcase the fibres are placed in an angle of $\pm 30^\circ$. This fibre orientation is a good

compromise compared with the optimal orientations for the torsion load and both bending loads. The fiber orientation in the rear end is +/- 45°. This is the best fibre orientation for torsion load but not the best for bending forces. This reinforcement improves the drive comfort due to reduced the bending stiffness. That is why this part can partly absorb high impulses from the back wheel.

Properties of the Frame

The weight of the carbon part of the developed bicycle frame is about 1600 g and for the necessary inserts 500 g. The inserts are made of steel and not optimized for minimum weight. One important criterion for the quality of a frame is the torque stiffness. For the determination of this value the frame is fixed at the back wheel axis and the steering unit is loaded in torsion. The force per degree of deformation is the value for the torque stiffness of the frame. This carbon frame reaches a torque stiffness of 55 N per degree. So, despite the difficult design this frame shows good mechanical properties.

ADVANTAGES OF TAILORED FIBRE PLACEMENT

In combination with innovative design and production techniques, TFP show excellent potential for a great variety of textile preforms with stress field aligned fibre placement and reinforcement in the third dimension. Its base on well established automated design and production technologies ensures the short time from design initiation to preform production and makes the TFP an exceptionally fast prototyping technique. Reproduceability is excellent.

FINAL REMARK

This paper reports on the technology of tailored fibre placement. By means of demonstrator parts the advantages and the possibilities of this technology are shown.

A separate paper reports on the design methodologies which promise the best exploitations of the TFP technology. Several of these methodologies were tested in their abilities to relieve a stress concentration in a notched composite. The manufacturing of these components, the testing setups used and results are presented in the separate paper.

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